

Original Research

Process and Quality of Prepared Beef Products with a Compound Improver

MAO Xiangxiang^{1,2}, YANG Tingxiao^{1,2}, YI Dan^{1,2}, YU Qiying^{1,2}, GUO Yirui^{1,2}, LI Jianzhou^{1,2*}, CHEN Xiaohua^{1,2*}, LUO Yunmei

¹ College of Life Sciences, Hengyang Normal University, No. 165 Huangbai Road, Yanfeng District, Hengyang, 421008, China

² Hunan Key Laboratory for Conservation and Utilization of Biological Resources in the Nanyue Mountainous Region, Hengyang Normal University, No. 165 Huangbai Road, Yanfeng District, Hengyang, 421008, China

Article history:

Received: 06 March 2026

Accepted: 29 March 2026

Published Online: 16 April 2026

*Correspondence:

Li JZ, Chen XH, College of Life Sciences, Hengyang Normal University, No. 165 Huangbai Road, Yanfeng District, Hengyang, 421008, China

How to cite this article:

MAO Xiangxiang, YANG Tingxiao, YI Dan, YU Qiying, GUO Yirui, LI Jianzhou, CHEN Xiaohua, LUO Yunmei (2026). *Process and Quality of prepared Beef products with a Compound Improver*. *North American Academic Research*, 9(3), 201-214. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19612395>

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations. **Copyright:** ©2025 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Abstract

To improve the quality of prepared beef, this study investigated the effects of papain (PP) addition level, konjac gum (KGM) addition level, soy protein isolate (SPI) addition level, and chicken powder (CPR) addition level on the texture, color, cooking yield, and sensory evaluation of prepared beef. Orthogonal experiments were conducted to optimize the marination formula for prepared beef, following single-factor experiments. The results showed that the optimal ratio of the compound improver was A₁B₁C₁D₁, i.e., papain at 0.1%, konjac gum at 1.5%, soy protein isolate at 0.5%, and chicken powder at 1.0%. The prepared beef obtained with this formula exhibited optimal performance in all measured indices, including a cooking yield of 80.17%, color values (L* = 34.02, a* = 18.57, b* = 12.57), and a comprehensive sensory score of 8.02, making it the optimal ratio within the experimental range. Under this ratio, all improvers exerted a synergistic effect: PP moderately hydrolyzed the muscle tissue to improve tenderness; KGM and SPI formed a composite gel network to reconstruct the tissue structure and enhance water-holding capacity; CPR optimized the flavor and taste. A favorable balance was achieved among all indices, providing practical process parameters for the processing of beef products.

Keywords: prepared beef; papain; soy protein isolate; konjac gum; chicken powder

Introduction

Prepared beef refers to an uncooked, non-instant meat product made primarily from fresh or frozen beef—with beef hind leg muscle generally being the preferred cut. It is produced through a series of processes including cutting and trimming, mixing with seasonings, marinating, tumbling, and packaging, then stored, transported, and sold under cold chain conditions^[1]. According to the competition analysis of the beef

industry, China has become the world's third-largest beef breeding and producing country, following the United States and Brazil. In terms of market demand, beef ranks second in global meat consumption, while China ranks third in the world in beef consumption, with downstream market demand for beef exceeding its supply^[2]. When consumers enjoy beef in restaurants, they are subject to various constraints such as time, location and price^[3]. In contrast, prepared beef is increasingly favored by the market due to its advantages of convenience in consumption, nutritional safety, ease of cooking and moderate price^[4]. It has been evident that prepared beef boasts a broad market prospect. However, prepared beef entered the Chinese market relatively late, and consumers awareness and acceptance of it are restricted by various factors^[5]. Therefore, the development of prepared beef is imperative to cater to the mass consumer groups.

The quality of prepared beef is the most crucial factor affecting consumers' product choices. Nevertheless, prepared beef available on the market is prone to problems such as tough texture, low digestibility, poor elasticity, and insufficient nutrition and flavor. Generally, the flavor of prepared beef products is adjusted and their texture is improved by adding seasoning accessories and additives, thereby enhancing the overall quality of prepared beef products to meet consumer demands. For instance, Liu Yajuan et al.^[6] reported that treatment of camel meat with papain (PP) could break down myofibrillar and connective tissue proteins, thereby reducing shear force and improving tenderness. Shuwen Lei et al.^[7] indicated that the main component of konjac gum(KGM) is glucomannan, which can insert into the gaps of the protein gel network and interact with it, maintaining the gel system and the secondary structure of proteins, enhancing water-holding capacity and gel strength, as well as improving the flavor, texture, moisture retention and structural properties of meat products. Liu Jingxue et al.^[8] stated that soy protein isolate (SPI) can improve the quality and increase the nutritional value of meat products. Li Meng et al.^[9] suggested that chicken powder (CPR) can enhance the umami taste and texture of chicken meat. The above studies have demonstrated that these four additives, namely papain, konjac gum, soy protein isolate and chicken powder, can effectively improve the quality of meat products through specific mechanisms.

Based on the above research, this study selected papain, konjac gum, soy protein isolate, and chicken powder as compound additives to investigate their effects on the texture, color, cooking yield, and sensory evaluation of prepared beef. Furthermore, an orthogonal test was conducted to determine the optimal combination of these additives, aiming to obtain a high-quality marination formula for prepared beef. This provides a reference for the development of premium prepared beef and its industrial production.

Materials and Methods

1.1 Materials

Water-Injected Beef (WIB, food grade) was purchased from Wangyi Industrial Group Hengyang Xiangjiang Department Store Co., Ltd. (Hengyang, China). Soy Sauce (SS, food grade) was purchased from Foshan Haitian (Gaoming) Flavoring & Food Co., Ltd. (Foshan, China). Oyster Sauce (OS, food grade) was purchased from Foshan Haitian (Suqian) Flavoring & Food Co., Ltd. (Suqian, China). White Granulated Sugar (WGS, food grade) was purchased from Yunnan Dianpeng Sugar Industry Co., Ltd. (Kunming, China). Edible Salt (ES, food grade) was purchased from Hunan Xiangheng Salt Chemical Co., Ltd. (Hengyang, China). Papain (PP, food grade) was purchased from Nanning Pangbo Bioengineering Co., Ltd. (Nanning, China). Konjac Gum (KGM, food grade) was purchased from Hubei Qiangsen Konjac Technology Co., Ltd. (Shiyan, China). Soy Protein Isolate (SPI, food grade) was purchased from Linyi Shansong Biological Products Co., Ltd. (Linyi, China). Chicken Powder (CPR, food grade) was purchased from Totole Food Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China).

1.2 Instruments and Equipment

TA-XT plus physical property Tester: Chaoji Instrument Co., Ltd.; JA5003 Analytical Balance: Shanghai puchun Metrological Instrument Co., Ltd.; CR-400 Colorimeter: KONICAMINOLTA; HNY-2102C Constant Temperature Oscillation Incubator: Tianjin Zhengnuo Instrument Co., Ltd.; MLS-3780 High-pressure Steam Sterilizer: Sanyo Electric Co., Ltd.; FS-190-220W Household Electric Food Slicer: pinyin (Foshan) Technology Co., Ltd.; SYG-2-4 Electric Thermostatic Water Bath: Tianjin Tester Instrument Co., Ltd.; VS-840-2 Clean Bench: Medical Equipment Factory of Shanghai Boxun Industrial Co., Ltd.; XYY-SYJG Non-stick Frying pan:

1.3 Methods

1.3.1 process flow of prepared beef

The production process of prepared beef is shown in Figure 1.

- (1) Selection of raw materials. Choose fresh and quarantine-qualified beef hind leg meat.
- (2) Slicing. Remove the fat and fascia from the beef, thickness of 0.8 cm. Weigh 100g of the meat slices, put them into a glass container, and set aside for later use.
- (4) Marination. Add the marinating ingredients in sequence (50% water, 1% salt, 1% sugar, 2% oyster sauce, 2% soy sauce, papain, konjac gum, soy protein isolate, chicken powder, based on the weight of the meat). put on food-grade gloves, mix them evenly, and knead and roll the beef for 10 minutes. After allowing the papain to activate for 30 minutes, seal the glass container with plastic wrap and place it in a refrigerator at 4 °C to marinate for 12 hours.
- (5) Packaging. Put the prepared beef into a vacuum bag for vacuum packaging, and store it in a refrigerator at -18°C for freezing.

Fig.1 Processing flow chart of prepared beef

1.3.2 Single-factor experimental design for prepared beef

Taking texture values, color difference values, cooking rate, and sensory evaluation as indicators, a single-factor experiment was conducted to study the effects of papain, konjac gum, soy protein isolate, and chicken powder on the quality of prepared beef. Based on Chinese national standards, enterprise standards, and the addition levels used in existing processed beef products on the market, the recommended dosage of papain is 0.1% - 0.3%, soy protein isolate 2% - 3%, konjac gum 0.5% - 2%, and chicken powder 2%. The experimental levels were set as follows: the addition amount of papain was 0.00%, 0.05%, 0.10%, 0.15%, 0.20%; the addition amount of konjac gum was 0.0%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%; the addition amount of soy protein isolate was 0%, 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%; and the addition amount of chicken powder was 0%, 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%. Among these indices, cooking yield, sensory score, a^* value, chewiness and springiness were considered the higher the better, while L^* value, b^* value, adhesiveness and hardness were the lower the better. According to the method of Kong et al.^[10], the weight coefficients were assigned as follows: cooking yield (25%), sensory score (25%), color values (20%, including L^* value 6%, a^* value 7% and b^* value 7%), and textural properties (30%, including hardness 8%, springiness 8%, chewiness 7% and cohesiveness 7%).

1.3.3 Orthogonal Experimental Design for prepared beef

The results of the single-factor experiment, with texture, color difference, cooking rate, and sensory evaluation as the investigation indicators, through the $L_9(3^4)$ orthogonal test, the addition amount of papain (A), the addition amount of konjac gum (B), the addition amount of soy protein isolate (C), and the addition amount of chicken powder (D) were selected as the investigation factors. Each factor was set with 3 levels for formula optimization to determine the optimal parameters of the prepared beef process. The orthogonal test design is shown in Table 1.

Table1 Coding Table of Factors and Levels for Orthogonal Experiment

Level	Factors (addition amount/%)			
	PP(A)	KGM(B)	SPI(C)	CP(D)
1	0.10	1.50	0.50	1.00
2	0.15	2.00	1.00	2.00
3	0.20	2.50	1.50	3.00

1.3.4 Determination of indicators

1.3.4.1 Determination of texture

A texture analyzer was used to determine the texture properties and shear force respectively. The specific methods and parameter settings for the determination of texture properties refer to the method of Kong Qi et al.^[10] with certain modifications. The cooked prepared beef was cut into 10 mm × 10 mm × 8 mm meat pieces along the direction of muscle fibers, and the determination was carried out in TPA mode. The parameters were set as follows: pre-test speed 2 mm/s, mid-test speed 2 mm/s, post-test speed 2 mm/s, compression ratio 40%, interval time between two presses 5 s, trigger force 50 g, probe distance 20 mm, and the probe was p/36 R. Each group of samples was measured in parallel 10 times, and the average value was taken.

1.3.4.2 Determination of color difference

The color difference was measured with reference to the method of Ni Shenyu et al.^[11] Using a standard white template as a control, prepared beef was randomly selected, and a colorimeter was used to determine the lightness value (L^*), redness value (a^*), and yellowness value (b^*) of the prepared beef respectively. Since the color of the meat surface varies with position, each group of samples was measured repeatedly 12 times at different positions on the meat surface, and the average value was taken.

1.3.4.3 Determination of cooking rate

Refer to the method by Su Nan et al.^[12] with certain modifications. Drain the prepared beef and use kitchen paper to dry the surface marinade from the prepared beef. Then, cut it into meat samples of uniform size, weight and record the mass before cooking as G_1 . place the samples in a cooking bag, heat them in a 78 °C water bath until the central temperature of the meat samples reaches 72 °C, maintain this temperature for 20 minutes, then cool to room temperature. Blot dry the surface moisture with absorbent paper, weigh and record the weight as G_2 .

Calculation formula: $L = G_2 / G_1 \times 100\%$

In the formula: L is the cooking rate, %; G_1 is the mass of the sample before cooking, g; G_2 is the mass of the sample after cooking, g.

1.3.4.4 Sensory evaluation

Referring to the method by Kong Qi et al.^[13], pour 5 g of edible oil into a dry flat-bottomed pan, spread 100 g of prepared beef evenly in the pan, and fry it over low heat using an induction cooker with a power of 350 W until both sides turn to the color of cooked meat. Immediately place it into an insulated container. The sensory evaluation panel consisted of 10 food professionals (with an equal number of males and females). Given the small sample size of the panel, the evaluation results might have a relatively high degree of dispersion. To address this, all panelists received unified training prior to the evaluation to calibrate the evaluation criteria and scales. Meanwhile, all samples were coded with random numbers for blind evaluation, with group labels removed; panelists were only informed of the coding information, thus ensuring the reliability and representativeness of the evaluation results. The sensory evaluation criteria were implemented

in accordance with ISO sensory evaluation standards and relevant specifications, and also referenced the method established by Kong Qi et al.^[13], as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Sensory evaluation criteria for prepared beef

indicator	weight coefficient	evaluation criteria	score
flavor	0.40	Unique flavor, no fishy smell or obvious sour taste of fermentation broth.	7-9
		Good flavor, with a slight fishy smell or other off-odors.	5-6
		Distinct fishy smell or other unusual odors, which affects consumption.	1-4
color and luster	0.20	Exhibits reddish brown or brownish red with uniform color.	7-9
		Exhibits reddish brown or brownish red with relatively uniform color.	5-6
		Shows pale, darkened or other abnormal colors with uneven color.	1-4
juiciness	0.20	Juicy and tasty	7-9
		The juice is relatively abundant, but the taste is slightly inferior.	5-6
		The juice is not plump, and the taste is poor.	1-4
tenderness	0.20	The meat is tender. It is easy to chew and swallow.	7-9
		The meat is relatively tender.	5-6
		The meat is tough and not easy to chew or swallow.	1-4

1.4 process validation

Based on the results of the orthogonal experiment, the optimal process parameters were obtained, and three parallel experiments were conducted for verification according to these parameters.

1.5 Data processing

The experimental results are expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA). Data processing was performed using SPSS 28.0 software (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$, determined by Student's t-test or ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. The figures were plotted using Origin 2021 software.

Results and Discussions

2.1 Analysis of the results of single-factor experiments on prepared beef

2.1.1 The effect of different auxiliary materials on the texture of prepared beef

Texture is a key indicator for ensuring the taste, quality stability, and market acceptance of prepared beef. As shown in Table 3, except for chicken powder, different auxiliary materials had significant differences in their effects on the texture characteristics, and these effects exhibited regular patterns with changes in addition level. For papain, in the initial stage of increasing its addition level, the hardness, chewiness, elasticity, and adhesiveness of prepared beef all showed an upward trend. At an addition level of 0.05%, the hardness, chewiness, and adhesiveness were significantly higher than those of the other four groups ($p < 0.05$), indicating texture deterioration such as harder meat, difficulty in chewing, tightness but poor elasticity. However, with a further increase in addition level, the moderate degradation effect of the enzyme on connective tissues and muscle fibers became prominent, making the meat softer, easier to chew, and the elasticity more reasonable. When the addition level of papain increased to 0.20% (or when the addition level was $\geq 0.2\%$, excessive tenderization tended to occur), excessive hydrolysis of muscle proteins occurred,

causing destruction of the three-dimensional protein structure and loss of structural support in muscle tissue, leading to an overly soft texture and a decline in elasticity of the prepared beef^[14,15]. This indicated that moderate addition of papain can reduce the hardness, chewiness, and adhesiveness of prepared beef, endow it with reasonable elasticity, and thereby improve the taste to meet consumer preferences. The addition of konjac gum significantly reduced the hardness and adhesiveness of prepared beef ($p < 0.05$) but had no significant effect on chewiness or elasticity. This phenomenon may be attributed to the fact that konjac gum forms a hydrated gel that lubricates the meat matrix, reducing resistance to biting and surface stickiness^[16,17]. Soy protein isolate had no significant effect on the chewiness or adhesiveness of prepared beef ($p > 0.05$) but generally showed a trend of increasing hardness with increasing addition level. It is speculated that the reason is that a denser gel network can be formed after the protein concentration increases, enhancing the supporting force of the meat structure^[18,19], resulting in increased meat hardness and difficulty in chewing. Only at an addition level of 1% did the prepared beef exhibit reduced hardness and adhesiveness, and increased chewiness and elasticity, which better meets the quality requirements of being elastic, tender, and juicy. Chicken powder had no significant effect on the texture of prepared beef ($p > 0.05$). However, with increasing addition level, hardness and adhesiveness showed a trend of first increasing and then decreasing, suggesting that appropriate addition of chicken powder can reduce the hardness and adhesiveness of prepared beef, thereby improving the taste.

Table 3 Effects of Different Excipients on the Texture of prepared Beef

auxiliary materials	addition amount (%)	Texture index			
		hardness	masticatory	elasticity	adhesiveness
PP	0.00	1436.710±414.800 ^a	864.513±310.135 ^a	0.854±0.075 ^{ab}	1010.225±351.423 ^a
	0.05	2218.666±465.417 ^b	1569.586±339.563 ^b	0.900±0.060 ^{ab}	1747.714±377.473 ^b
	0.10	1131.200±292.925 ^a	806.440±299.655 ^a	0.976±0.239 ^b	824.680±252.217 ^a
	0.15	1341.971±676.357 ^a	714.340±404.306 ^a	0.803±0.092 ^a	880.397±490.430 ^a
	0.20	1278.849±485.592 ^a	804.55±373.426 ^a	0.886±0.169 ^{ab}	892.646±381.120 ^a
KGM	0.00	1375.150±593.169 ^a	2210.979±3771.593 ^a	1.545±1.637 ^a	1013.985±512.203 ^a
	0.50	703.060±412.411 ^b	846.638±745.476 ^a	2.084±1.948 ^a	476.141±315.782 ^b
	1.00	782.580±443.503 ^b	1024.899±1390.451 ^a	1.587±1.038 ^a	597.942±363.641 ^b
	1.50	804.110±365.050 ^b	719.827±528.244 ^a	1.472±1.119 ^a	556.819±306.066 ^b
	2.00	560.980±296.412 ^b	1363.509±1204.773 ^a	3.221±1.605 ^a	385.638±234.621 ^b
SPI	0.00	806.472±53.540 ^{ab}	1040.127±237.339 ^a	1.736±0.324 ^{ab}	630.712±43.627 ^a
	1.00	677.938±74.119 ^b	1778.358±253.943 ^a	3.058±0.493 ^a	570.532±46.000 ^a
	2.00	900.890±114.478 ^{ab}	1335.187±542.760 ^a	1.159±0.203 ^b	674.849±93.446 ^a
	3.00	1053.791±86.826 ^a	1347.728±218.076 ^a	1.82±0.337 ^{ab}	803.16±68.686 ^a
	4.00	992.586±106.729 ^{ab}	1330.631±220.634 ^a	2.009±0.388 ^{ab}	706.439±90.125 ^a
CPR	0.00	856.842±80.915 ^a	2088.903±383.650 ^a	3.045±0.372 ^a	653.744±70.467 ^a
	1.00	1056.995±144.249 ^a	1917.537±305.606 ^a	2.820±0.489 ^a	794.816±102.906 ^a
	2.00	949.034±69.520 ^a	1409.982±386.070 ^a	2.001±0.460 ^a	664.150±54.897 ^a

auxiliary materials	addition amount (%)	Texture index			
		hardness	masticatory	elasticity	adhesiveness
	3.00	889.472±162.166 ^a	1445.563±340.978 ^a	2.046±0.510 ^a	565.801±93.77 ^a
	4.00	788.759±72.343 ^a	1694.426±318.594 ^a	3.096±0.536 ^a	598.811±50.799 ^a

Note: Values are Means ± SD, each value in the table is the mean of ten replications.

^{a,b}Values with different letters in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

2.1.2 The influence of different auxiliary materials on the color difference of prepared beef

Color difference is an important indicator for quantifying the quantitative difference in food color perception. It is usually characterized by the L* value (lightness), a* value (red-green chromaticity), and b* value (yellow-blue chromaticity). Changes in color directly affect consumers' visual perception and purchasing decisions. As shown in Table 4, different auxiliary materials had different effects on the color difference of prepared beef, and their effects showed regular trends with changes in addition level. For papain, its addition significantly increased the a* value of prepared beef ($p < 0.05$) but had no significant effect on the L* or b* values. With increasing addition level, the a* value showed a gradual upward trend. It is speculated that the reason may be that papain fully exposes myoglobin by hydrolyzing proteins, thereby enhancing the bright red color of prepared beef. Konjac gum had no generally significant effect on the color difference of prepared beef. However, with increasing addition level, the L, a, and b* values all showed a trend of first increasing and then decreasing. Among these, the L* and b* values peaked at an addition level of 1%, while the a* value was highest at 2%, indicating that an appropriate amount of konjac gum is beneficial for improving the lightness and yellowness of prepared beef, whereas excessive addition can enhance redness. Soy protein isolate had no significant effect on the color difference of prepared beef ($p > 0.05$). However, with increasing addition level, both the a* and b* values showed an upward trend. It is speculated that this is partly related to the pale-yellow characteristic of soy protein isolate itself, which leads to increased yellowness; on the other hand, its interaction with muscle tissue may promote myoglobin oxidation, thereby increasing redness. Chicken powder also had no significant effect on the color difference of prepared beef ($p > 0.05$) but exhibited a specific pattern with changes in addition level. The L* and a* values first increased and then decreased, while the b* value first decreased and then increased. This indicates that excessive addition of chicken powder leads to a dark yellow coloration of prepared beef, whereas an appropriate addition can effectively improve lightness and redness, reduce yellowness, and give the product a bright red color that is more preferred by consumers.

Table 4 Effects of Different Excipients on the Color of prepared Beef

auxiliary materials	addition amount (%)	Color index		
		L*	a*	b*
PP	0.00	34.058±0.698 ^{ab}	15.850±0.530 ^c	14.948±0.674 ^{ab}
	0.05	32.262±0.396 ^b	16.562±0.611 ^{bc}	15.136±0.610 ^{ab}
	0.10	32.666±0.570 ^{ab}	19.118±0.638 ^{ab}	17.025±0.760 ^a
	0.15	33.028±0.550 ^{ab}	19.063±0.514 ^{ab}	13.472±0.981 ^b
	0.20	34.894±0.890 ^a	19.419±0.883 ^a	14.887±0.882 ^{ab}
KGM	0.00	33.12±3.85 ^a	18.14±4.33 ^a	15.84±2.69 ^a
	0.50	32.36±2.53 ^a	19.96±2.12 ^{ab}	14.93±2.19 ^a
	1.00	35.92±2.37 ^a	18.56±2.10 ^a	16.43±1.70 ^a
	1.50	34.12±5.03 ^a	17.43±3.88 ^a	14.94±3.15 ^a
SPI	2.00	33.24±0.90 ^a	21.93±1.53 ^b	15.92±2.75 ^a
	0.00	38.35±1.41 ^a	17.385±0.657 ^a	15.906±0.553 ^a
	1.00	38.72±0.752 ^a	17.715±0.605 ^a	16.182±0.552 ^a

auxiliary materials	addition amount (%)	Color index		
		L*	a*	b*
CPR	2.00	36.401±0.781 ^a	19.505±0.895 ^a	16.508±1.173 ^a
	3.00	38.71±0.600 ^a	19.8±0.594 ^a	14.202±1.469 ^a
	4.00	37.421±0.829 ^a	19.128±0.631 ^a	17.518±0.952 ^a
	0.00	42.714±0.435 ^a	18.607±0.652 ^{ab}	17.881±0.690 ^{ab}
	1.00	42.36±0.917 ^a	20.307±0.700 ^a	17.016±2.077 ^{ab}
	2.00	43.998±0.601 ^a	19.42±0.526 ^{ab}	11.678±1.581 ^b
	3.00	43.553±1.476 ^a	16.526±1.327 ^b	11.975±1.993 ^b
	4.00	40.743±0.669 ^a	16.282±0.671 ^b	18.576±1.279 ^a

Note: Values are Means ± SD, each value in the table is the mean of ten replications.

a,b,c Values with different letters in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

2.1.3 The effect of different auxiliary materials on the cooking rate of prepared beef

The cooking yield refers to the ratio of the retained mass of seasoned beef to its initial mass after cooking. It plays a crucial role in various aspects, including product quality, processing efficiency, and consumer experience. As shown in Figure 2, different auxiliary materials had varying effects on the cooking yield of seasoned beef. As shown in Figure 2A, the addition of papain generally improved the cooking yield. With increasing addition level, the cooking yield showed a trend of first increasing, then decreasing, and then slightly increasing again. When the addition level reached 0.2%, the cooking yield peaked, indicating that papain has a certain water-retaining effect on seasoned beef. As shown in Figure 2B, konjac gum had no significant effect on the cooking yield of seasoned beef ($p > 0.05$). With increasing addition level, the cooking yield exhibited a fluctuating pattern: first increasing, then decreasing, and then increasing again. The highest cooking yield was observed at an addition level of 0.5%, while the yields at 1% and 1.5% were lower than that of the group without added konjac gum. This suggests that a low dose of konjac gum may have a positive effect on the cooking yield, whereas excessive addition is detrimental to the water retention of the product. As shown in Figure 2C, soy protein isolate had no significant effect on the cooking yield of seasoned beef, but the cooking yield of all addition groups was higher than that of the non-added group. This is attributed to the following mechanisms: the dense three-dimensional gel network formed by soy protein isolate physically entraps water via its porous structure, reducing water migration and loss; its active groups cross-link with muscle proteins, thereby enhancing tissue integrity, increasing water-binding sites, and stabilizing bound water; additionally, the emulsifying film formed by its adsorption at the water-lipid interface reduces interfacial tension to prevent water-lipid separation, and its hydrophilic groups form hydrogen bonds with water molecules to improve the hydration capacity of the system, further mitigating water loss^[20,21]. These findings indicate that soy protein isolate has a certain water-retaining effect on seasoned beef. As shown in Figure 2D, the cooking yield at a chicken powder addition level of 2% was significantly higher than that at 1% ($p < 0.05$), and extremely significantly higher than that at 4% ($p < 0.01$). Chicken powder improved the water-holding capacity of prepared beef through the synergistic effects of hydration adsorption, molecular cross-linking, and viscosity thickening. Specifically, the hydrophilic groups in its saccharides and amino acids formed hydrogen bonds with water molecules, converting free water into bound water via hydration, thus reducing water migration. Saccharides underwent Maillard cross-linking with muscle proteins, and amino acids bound to the active sites of proteins, jointly enhancing the structural integrity of beef tissue and improving the hydration capacity of muscle proteins to stabilize bound water. In addition, the hydrated hydrophilic components increased the system viscosity, formed a protective film on the beef surface, filled the gaps between muscle fibers, and slowed down the migration and volatilization of water, thereby achieving stable water retention.

Fig.2 Effects of different excipients on the cooking rate of prepared beef. (A) papain (B)konjac gum (C)soy protein isolate (D)chicken powder. Data represent mean \pm SD (n = 10 tests / treatment). Treatment groups marked with distinct letters differ significantly from each other (ANOVA with Tukey's HSD, $p < 0.05$).

2.1.4 The influence of different auxiliary materials on the sensory properties of prepared beef

Sensory evaluation is a core index that determines consumer acceptance and market competitiveness of food, as it directly reflects the eating experience quality of products. As shown in Figure 3, different auxiliary materials had varying degrees of impact on the sensory quality of prepared beef. As shown in Figure 3A, the sensory scores of the papain-added groups were generally higher than those of the group without added papain. With increasing addition level, the sensory scores showed an upward trend. When the addition level reached 0.15%, the score peaked. At this level, the product presented a uniform brownish-red color, a rich beef flavor, abundant juiciness, and tender meat, resulting in the best eating experience. This indicates that papain can effectively improve the tenderness of prepared beef^[22]. As shown in Figure 3B, konjac gum had a positive regulatory effect on sensory quality. At addition levels of 0.5%, 1.5%, and 2.0%, the sensory scores were all relatively high, with the 1.5% addition group achieving the highest score. The prepared beef exhibited abundant juiciness and tender, smooth meat. This was attributed to the ability of konjac gum to absorb and fix a large amount of water in the muscle tissue gaps after dissolution, thereby maintaining product juiciness. As shown in Figure 3C, the effect of soy protein isolate on sensory scores exhibited a dose-dependent pattern: first increasing, then decreasing, and then slowly rising again. When the addition level was 1.0%, the score reached its peak. Under the optimal conditions, the prepared beef showed a unique flavor and desirable color. However, when the addition level was further increased, problems such as uneven color and poor taste occurred, indicating that adding an appropriate amount of soy protein isolate can effectively improve the flavor quality of prepared beef. As shown in Figure 3D, with an increase in the addition level of chicken powder, the sensory scores displayed a continuous upward trend. Specifically, the flavor of the prepared beef gradually became stronger, the juiciness became more abundant, and the meat tenderness became more moderate. These improvements were closely related to the flavor-enhancing effects of the spices and monosodium glutamate components in chicken powder^[23], indicating that chicken powder can effectively optimize the sensory performance of prepared beef.

Fig.3 Effects of Different Excipients on the Sensory Quality of prepared Beef. (A) papain (B)konjac gum (C)soy protein isolate (D)chicken powder.

In summary, different addition amounts of papain, konjac gum, soy protein isolate, and chicken powder had varying effects on the texture, color, cooking yield, and sensory evaluation of prepared beef.

2.2 Analysis of orthogonal test results

According to the results of the single-factor experiment, the orthogonal experiment was conducted in accordance with $L_9(3^4)$. With texture, color difference, cooking rate, and sensory evaluation as the assessment indicators, the results of the orthogonal experiment were shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Results of orthogonal experiment

indicator	serial number									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Sensory evaluation	7.02	6.92	6.88	7.08	6.82	7.20	6.32	6.90	7.02	
Cooking rate	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.86	0.72	0.88	0.86	0.86	
Texture index	hardness	877.16	821.10	890.82	953.28	1090.11	805.76	1171.12	1361.85	1790.24
	chewability	1981.01	2001.14	1662.03	1268.74	1128.88	873.48	1008.27	1415.22	1699.72
	elasticity	3.00	3.35	2.83	2.03	1.60	1.43	1.20	1.39	1.52
	adhesiveness	622.81	611.78	654.73	677.84	778.03	556.95	853.57	970.36	1324.44
Color difference index	L* value	40.13	37.31	38.33	35.47	39.20	35.98	35.77	37.49	37.07
	a* value	18.48	18.14	18.46	16.82	16.79	15.76	16.12	14.71	16.28
	b* value	8.40	14.17	15.24	15.94	14.66	15.65	14.60	11.60	14.73

It can be seen from Table 6 that the order of influence on the sensory properties of prepared beef was $C > A > B = D$. The main factor affecting sensory evaluation was factor C (the amount of soy protein isolate added), followed by factor A (the amount of papain added), and the optimal combination was $A_2B_2C_1D_1$.

The order of influence on cooking rate was $A > B = C > D$. The main factor affecting cooking rate was A (the amount of papain added), and the optimal combination was $A_3B_2C_3D_1$.

The order of influence on hardness was $A > D > C > B$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_1C_1D_2$; the order of influence on elasticity was $A > C > B > D$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_2C_2D_3$; the order of influence on adhesiveness was $A > D > C > B$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_1C_1D_2$; and the order of influence on chewiness was $A > C > D > B$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_2C_2D_1$. Based on a comprehensive analysis of the four texture indicators, factor A (amount of papain added) and factor C (amount of soy protein isolate added) had a greater impact on the texture of prepared beef, whereas factor B (amount of konjac gum added) had a smaller impact.

The order of influence on the L* value was $D > A > C > B$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_2C_1D_1$; the order of influence on the a* value was $A > C > B > D$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_1C_3D_1$; and the order of influence on the b* value was $C > A > B > D$, with the optimal combination being $A_1B_1C_1D_1$. Based on a comprehensive analysis of the three-color indicators, factor A (amount of papain added) had a greater impact on the color of prepared beef, followed by factor C (amount of soy protein isolate added), while factor B (amount of konjac gum added) had a smaller impact.

Based on the comprehensive range analysis results, the sensory properties, cooking yield, texture, and color of prepared beef are greatly affected by factor A (amount of papain added) and factor C (amount of soy protein isolate added). Therefore, the first level was adopted for both factors: the amount of papain added was 0.1%, and the amount of soy protein isolate added was 0.5%. Factor D (chicken powder) is the main factor affecting the L* value of prepared beef; thus, the first level was adopted, with the amount of chicken powder added being 1.0%. Factor B (konjac gum) has a relatively small impact on the quality of prepared beef; accordingly, the first level was adopted, with the amount of konjac gum added being 1.5%.

To sum up, following the method of Kong Qi et al.^[10], the optimal combination obtained by the comprehensive balance method was $A_1B_1C_1D_1$, i.e., papain at 0.1%, konjac gum at 1.5%, soy protein isolate at 0.5%, and chicken powder at 1.0%.

Table 6 Range analysis of prepared beef

indicator	factor	k ₁	k ₂	k ₃	range (R)	primary and secondary factors	Optimal combination
Sensory evaluation	A	6.94	7.03	6.75	0.29	C>A>B=D	A ₂ B ₂ C ₁ D ₁
	B	6.81	6.88	6.74	0.14		
	C	7.04	7.01	6.67	0.37		
	D	6.95	6.81	6.95	0.14		
Cooking rate	A	0.82	0.79	0.87	0.07	A>B=C>D	A ₃ B ₂ C ₃ D ₁
	B	0.83	0.84	0.79	0.05		
	C	0.80	0.83	0.85	0.05		
	D	0.84	0.80	0.83	0.04		
hardness	A	863.03	949.72	1441.07	578.04	A>D>C>B	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ D ₂
	B	1000.52	1091.02	1162.27	161.75		
	C	1014.93	1188.21	1050.68	173.28		
	D	1157.72	932.66	1068.65	225.06		
elasticity	A	3.06	1.69	1.37	1.69	A>C>B>D	A ₁ B ₂ C ₂ D ₃
	B	2.08	2.11	1.93	0.19		
	C	1.94	2.30	1.88	0.42		
	D	2.04	1.99	2.08	0.09		
adhesiveness	A	629.77	670.94	1049.46	419.69	A>D>C>B	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ D ₂
	B	718.07	786.72	845.37	127.30		
	C	716.71	871.35	762.11	154.65		
	D	908.43	674.10	767.64	234.33		
chewability	A	1881.39	1090.37	1374.40	791.03	A>C>D>B	A ₂ B ₃ C ₃ D ₂
	B	1419.34	1515.08	1411.74	103.34		
	C	1423.23	1656.53	1266.39	390.14		
	D	1603.20	1294.30	1448.66	308.90		
L* value	A	38.59	36.88	36.78	1.81	D>A>C>B	A ₁ B ₂ C ₁ D ₁
	B	37.12	38.00	37.13	0.88		
	C	37.87	36.62	37.77	1.25		
	D	38.80	36.35	37.10	2.45		
a* value	A	18.36	16.46	15.70	2.66	A>C>B>D	A ₁ B ₁ C ₃ D ₁
	B	17.14	16.54	16.83	0.60		
	C	16.31	17.08	17.13	0.81		
	D	17.18	16.67	16.66	0.52		
b* value	A	12.61	15.41	13.64	2.81	C>A>B>D	A ₁ B ₁ C ₁ D ₁
	B	12.98	13.48	15.20	2.22		
	C	11.88	14.95	14.83	3.06		
	D	12.60	14.81	14.26	2.21		

2.3 Verification test

The prepared beef was marinated using the optimal process parameters obtained from the orthogonal experiment. After three repeated verifications, the hardness of the prepared beef was 745.02, the chewiness was 1178.73, the elasticity was 2.57, and the adhesiveness was 581.32, indicating moderate hardness and good resilience. The L* value was 34.02, the a* value was 18.57, and the b* value was 12.57, showing a cherry red

color^[24] with moderate brightness. The cooking yield was 80.17%, and the sensory score was 8.02, which was higher than that of any group in the orthogonal experiment. These results indicate that the prepared beef optimized with the orthogonal experiment process parameters exhibited the best quality and sensory properties.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effects of papain (PP), konjac gum (KGM), soy protein isolate (SPI), and chicken powder (CPR) on the texture, color, cooking yield, and sensory evaluation of prepared beef. The processing technology of prepared beef was optimized through single-factor and orthogonal experiments. The results showed that the optimal ratio of the compound improver was A₁B₁C₁D₁, i.e., papain at 0.1%, konjac gum at 1.5%, soy protein isolate at 0.5%, and chicken powder at 1.0%. The prepared beef obtained with this formula exhibited the optimal performance in all measured indices, including a cooking yield of 80.17%, color values (L* = 34.02, a* = 18.57, b* = 12.57), and a comprehensive sensory score of 8.02, making it the optimal ratio within the experimental range. Under this ratio, all improvers exerted a synergistic effect: PP moderately hydrolyzed the muscle tissue to improve tenderness; KGM and SPI formed a composite gel network to reconstruct the tissue structure and enhance water-holding capacity; CPR optimized the flavor and taste. A favorable balance was achieved among all indices, providing practical process parameters for the processing of beef products.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research supported by College Students' Innovation and Entrepreneurship Training Program Project of Hunan Province (grant numbers S202410546011, S202412659008); Scientific Research Fund of Hunan Provincial Education Department (grant number 23A0512).

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] WANG W, ZENG M, CHEN Q, et al. Influence of phosphate Marinades on the Quality and Flavor Characteristics of prepared Beef[J]. *Molecules*,2025,30(202):1-14.
- [2] XUAN WF, YANG XR, DAI ZQ, et al. Effect of Cold plasma Combined with Modified Atmosphere packaging on the Storage Quality of prepared Beef[J]. *Meat Research*,2025,39(6):46-53.
- [3] CHENG W, YANG Y. Research and analysis of beef price drivers in China[J]. *Academic Journal of Business and Management*,2025,7(1),205-210.
- [4] DENG JC, ZHENG JG, MAO XX, et al. Effect of Novel Composite Antifreeze Agent on the Quality of Marinated Beef after Repeated Freeze and Thaw Cycles[J]. *Journal of Fujian polytechnic Normal University*,2025,43(05):62-71.
- [5] GARCIA V, BRANDAO PA, WICKERSHAM AT, et al. Experiential learning improves college student perceived understanding and strengthens their perceptions of the beef industry[J]. *Translational Animal Science*,2025,9(1):1-9.
- [6] LIU YJ, MING L, DA LC, et al. Optimization of the Ultrasonic-papain Combined Tenderization process for Camel Meat and Its Impact on Quality Attributes[J]. *Science and Technology of Food Industry*,2026,47(6):233-241.
- [7] LEI SW, ZHAO CY, MIAO Y, et al. Konjac glucomannan: A key ingredient for controlling fibrous structure formation in walnut protein and wheat gluten meat analogues during the high-moisture extrusion process[J]. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*,2025,117588(220):1-14.
- [8] LIU JX, LIANG XH, ZHANG GQ, et al. Study on the Application of Soy protein Isolate in Meat products[J]. *Cereals and Oils processing*,2023,48(01):41-44.
- [9] LI M, XU YJ. Research progress on Influencing Factors of Flavor of Salted Chicken powder[J]. *Modern Food*,2023,29(19):27-30.
- [10] KONG Q. Development of Lactic Acid Bacteria Fermentation Broth-assisted prepared beef products and Study of Quality Changes during Freezing[D]. Yangzhou University,2023.10
- [11] NI SY, LI Q, LI P, et al. Effects of Different Beef Parts on the Quality and Volatile Components of Conditioned

- Steaks[J]. *Science and of Food Industry*, 2025, 46(24): 136–145.
- [12] SU N, MA Z, WANG X, et al. Study on the differences of slaughter performance and meat quality characteristics of Xinjiang Brown Cattle by different feeding methods[J]. *Xinjiang Agricultural Sciences*,2024,61(12):3105-3112.
- [13] KONG Q, RAO SQ, HANG F. Effect of lactic acid bacteria fermentation broth on the quality and volatile flavor compounds of marinated beef[J]. *Food and Fermentation Industries*,2023,49(21):74-82.
- [14] ZHANG Hao, GAO Zhen. Effects of papain on the quality of pork chops[J]. *China Food Additives*,2023,34(7):228-233.
- [15] CRISTINA B, MOHAMMAD H, MARIA A M, et al. The influence of the interaction of sous-vide cooking time and papain concentration on tenderness and technological characteristics of meat products[J].*Meat Science*,2021,108491(177):1-9
- [16] DU TS, LIU Y, Wang XY, et al. Optimization of plant- based Meatball Based on principal Component Analysis and Response Surface Methodology[J]. *Journal of the Chinese Cereals and Oils Association*,2024,39(07): 110-119.
- [17] Singthong J, Aree O J, Oonsivilai R. Enhancing low-fat meat products: Konjac glucomannan and lotus seed flour as functional ingredients in Moo-Yor[J]. *Food Chemistry Advances*,2025,101022(7):1-8.
- [18] LI LX, ZHAO XX, KONG Baohua. Effect of Soy protein Isolate on Quality Characteristics of Ready-to-Eat Restructured Beef products[J]. *Meat Research*,2016,30(10):7-12.
- [19] Fu J, Zhan Z, Duan Q, et al. Application of soybean protein isolates-polysaccharides hybrid emulsion gels as alternative fats in fabricating plant-based meats with two-phase[J]. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 2025, 117524(218):1-10.
- [20] ZHENG YH. The preparation and application of soybean protein isolate/gelatin composite emulsion gel in meat sausage[D]. Chengdu University,2025.
- [21] WAN W, ZHANG R, GAO L, et al. Mechanisms of heat-activated soy protein isolate-chitosan oligosaccharide complexation: Synergistic interactions for enhanced gelation[J]. *Carbohydrate Polymers* ,2026,124703(374):1-13.
- [22] Rosaria M, Antonella M D, Mariangela C, et al. Proteomics in bovine semitendinosus muscle to assess emerging strategies based on papain injection and ultrasounds on meat tenderization process[J]. *Meat Science*,2023,109147(200):1-11.
- [23] ZHU B, XU W, DAI Z, et al. Chicken Meal as a Fishmeal Substitute: Effects on Growth, Antioxidants, and Digestive Enzymes in *Lithobates catesbeianus*[J]. *Animals*,2024,2200(14):1-13.
- [24] Krell J, Müller T, Poveda-Arteaga A, et al. Effect of Different Oxygen Atmospheres on Color Stability of Modified Atmosphere packaged Beef Using Non-Invasive Measurement[J]. *Applied Sciences*,2025,8987(15):1-19.

